

Institutional Readiness and User Requirements for the Development of Nigerian Research Information Management Systems

Manir Abdullahi Kamba

Department of Library and Information Sciences, Bayero University Kano
manirung@yahoo.com (corresponding author)

Umar Balarabe

Department of Computer Science, Bayero University, Kano
Ubalarabe.cs@buk.edu.ng

Yusuff Tijjani

Center for Information Technology, Bayero University, Kano
Ytijjani.cit@buk.edu.ng

Abstract

Background

The paper investigated the institutional readiness and user requirements for the development of Nigerian Research Information Management System. Three research objectives guided the study, which include to find out the level of institutional readiness towards the development of NRIMS, determine the user requirements for the design and development for NRIMS, and identify the challenges associated with the design and development for NRIMS for Universities in Northwest, Nigeria.

Method: Quantitative research methodology using survey design was adopted for the study. Online surveys and questionnaires were the instrument used for data collection. The population of the study was 165 comprising 21 research administrators, 105 researchers, 35 librarians and 7 university management staff. Quantitative data from surveys was analyzed using statistical software (SPSS version 16) was used, descriptive statistics using measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion were used to identify trends and patterns.

Findings/Results: The findings showed that more than half of the universities under study were partially ready in terms of management, technology, process and people's readiness. The findings also showed that all the universities under study indicated that

they required all the parameters (User Registration, Product Search and Filtering, Online Ordering and Payment, consistent visual design, Online Ordering and Payment, Clear Call-to-Action Buttons, intuitive form design, Responsive Design and intuitive navigation) of the requirements for the development of NRIMS. The study identified in adequate funding, lack infrastructure, limited technical expertise and poor data management practices as the challenges associated with the design and development of NRIMS.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the identification of institutional readiness and user requirements for design and development of NRIMS can effectively improve the efficiency of research management in the Universities of the Northwest Nigeria, with minimal challenges.

Recommendations: The study recommended amongst others that Universities in Northwest Nigeria should invest in the provision of ICT infrastructure, provision of more funding to support the design and development of NRIMS

Keywords: Institutional readiness, user requirements, Nigeria, NRIMS, information system

Introduction

University's core business is research. It is key to a university's reputation and is central to its mission. Nationally, governments recognize that research is critical for expanding the university knowledge base, driving improvements in teaching, and advancing social and economic gains. Developing and managing a research portfolio is not easy. In this regard, the practice of research information management (RIM) is becoming more important as the research environment becomes increasingly complex, competitive and globalized. At the same time, universities are looking for ways to identify strengths, demonstrate engagement, and measure the impact of their research and educational programming. (Bryant et al., 2017, p. 10).

National mandates and requirements of national funding agencies regarding open access and research data management are creating added incentives for universities to showcase their publications and make them available in an open-access format. Libraries are well situated to offer expertise throughout the adoption of a research information management system by a university. In aligning themselves with the wider strategic plans of the institution, libraries can use this as a platform to further their own goals and

communicate their value and place in the institution by championing open access, ensuring discoverability and supporting researchers.

A Research Information Management System (RIMS) captures information about the current research activities of a university, aggregating, curating, managing and utilizing information and metadata to provide a view of research output and its impact on the institution (Bryant et al., 2017, p. 7). RIMS enables institutions to manage this information in combination with other valuable data such as researchers' affiliations, publications, research data, funding applications and reviews, budgets, academic service and honors, and impact measures. Institutions may also include internal measures of scholarly activity such as courses, graduate student supervision and committee contributions. Science Europe distinguishes research information management (RIMS) from research data management, noting that RIMS deals with "data about research activities rather than research data generated by researchers" (Science Europe, 2016, p. 3).

Varying terminology is used to denote RIMS. The term Current Research Information System (CRIS) tends to be used in Europe, with the initial C sometimes being dropped. In North America, the terms used vary more widely, and systems may be known as Research Networking Systems (RNS), Research Profiling Systems (RPS) or Faculty Activity Reporting (FAR) (Bryant et al., 2017, p. 7). In Europe, euroCRIS, a not-for-profit association that includes research administration experts, emerged as a leader in developing standards and practices for RIM, and maintains the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) standard (Science Europe, 2016, p. 7). Science Europe (2016) has proposed a set of common principles for RIMS to enhance interoperability. Nigeria currently lacks similar standards nationally and locally at different universities although this research project is trying to develop a prototype or draft RIMS that could serve as a standard tentatively titled the Nigerian Research Information Management Systems, covering type of activity, fields of research and socio-economic objectives.

In Europe, the implementation of Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) began more than a decade ago (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Jefferey & Asserson, 2008; Joint, 2008; Scholze & Mayer, 2012), for instance with the national adoption of Pure in Denmark, adoption in Austria at several universities including the University of Vienna, Ontanuniversität Leoben and Graz University of Technology (Greil, 2015) and with the University of St. Andrews in Scotland choosing to replace their in house CRIS with Pure (Clements & McCutcheon, 2014, p. 201). Atira, from which Pure was developed, was

created in Denmark in 2002 in Aalborg (Jorgensen, 2016) and there was significant government support behind the mandatory adoption of Pure at Danish universities. Since then, Danish librarians have deftly used the system to extract strategic research metrics and analyze trends (Price, 2008; Wien et al., 2016). EuroCRIS, also founded in 2002, has helped European institutions to implement effective CRIS platforms and standards. The euroCRIS mandate is: “to promote cooperation within and share knowledge among the research information community and interoperability of research information through CERIF, the Common European Research Information Format. Areas of interest also cover research databases, CRIS related data like scientific datasets, (open access) institutional repositories, as well as data access and exchange mechanisms, standards and guidelines and best practice for CRIS” (“What is euroCRIS”, n.d.).

NRIMS can be used to create researcher profile management, often with interoperability with systems and faculty evaluation processes; it can facilitate robust recording of faculty research and publication activities. Researcher profiles can also be used as public-facing faculty expertise directories (Bryant et al., 2017, p. 9). Faculty activity recording, including collecting and managing information related to scholarly activities such as teaching, graduate student supervision, tenure and evaluation processes, or institutional service, can be used for faculty evaluation and promotion purposes.

With the development of NRIMS data and metadata related to research activities, it can be aggregated within the system and can be used in reporting, decision-making, planning and accreditation for departments and the institution. Research impact can also be measured via connections with external sources such as Scopus and other related databases. For researchers, NRIMS can represent a way of streamlining and enhancing their research process and presence and making their work more visible. Researchers can generate information to use in professional profiles and annual reports and can develop research networks and identify potential research partners. Having all the processes, information and activities related to a research project together in one place can lighten the workload of faculty. However, Korberg (2016) found that a lack of faculty engagement due to time constraints and administrative burden was one of the anticipated barriers to the proposed RIMS (p. 26). Based on the foregoing, the study is designed to develop a prototype for Research Information Management Systems (RIMS) that can be used to capture information about the current research activities of a university, aggregating, curating, managing and utilizing information and metadata to provide a view of research output and impact for the institution.

As the value of systems for documenting research activity began to gain attention, and technical solutions were reaching maturity, universities began to turn their attention to implementing RIMS (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Jeffery & Asserson, 2008). The literature about RIMS includes articulations of their potential value, accounts of local implementations, and discussions about metadata and research evaluation.

Several authors describe the value of RIMS for user groups including researchers, administrators, funding agencies, innovators and media (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Buchmayer et al., 2014; Grenz et al., 2017; Jeffery & Asserson, 2008; Scholze & Maier, 2012). RIMS can facilitate the review of previous research (Grenz, 2017; Jeffery & Asserson, 2008); document the research performance of individuals and institutions (Akoev et al., 2016; Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Jeffery & Asserson, 2008); support administrative functions such as annual reports and researcher profiles (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Scholze & Maier, 2012); integrate workflows in areas such as Article Processing Charges (APCs) (Clarke & Bussey, 2018, p.218); facilitate the preservation of research outputs and data (Clarke & Bussey, 2018; Schopfel et al., 2017; Simons et al., 2017) provide access to material for teaching and learning (Jeffery & Asserson, 2008, p. 73), and enable the public and media to have easier access to quality information to popularize research (Buchmayer et al.; Jeffery & Asserson, 2008). Dorch (2015) points out that the Pure system at the University of Southern Denmark and in other Danish institutions works in conjunction with the Danish Open Access strategy to enable scholarly communication and research evaluation (n.p.).

Accounts for CRIS implementation provide descriptions of the best practices and challenges experienced during the process. In their implementation of Pure at the University of Vienna, Buchmayer et al. (2014) found that participation by stakeholders at an early stage is important, as is the composition of the implementation team. The University of Vienna also holds annual meetings for “power-users” and representatives from faculties (Greil, 2015, n.p.). McGrath and Cox (2014) note that during the implementation of Pure at King’s College London, regular presentations were made at departmental meetings, to create a better level of awareness than launch events (p. 303). The team also conducted semi-structured interviews with stakeholders across the institution (p. 303). At the University of St Andrews, the team mapped workflows against research lifecycles and established a connection between Open Access and CRIS processes (Fina & Proven, 2017, p. 237).

Challenges reported by institutions included increased workload (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Buchmayer et al., 2014), the need to develop new skills, the engagement of stakeholders (Bevan & Harrington, 2011, p. 29), difficulties in ingesting information into the system (Grenz et al., 2017, p. 178), and creating a comprehensive research information management environment (Grenz et al., 2017, p. 180). Jeffery and Asserson (2008) articulate the advantages of formal metadata and identify issues regarding interoperability of metadata in CRIS (p. 79). Bevan and Harrington (2011) note the trade-off between data quality in the CRIS and workload for those entering and validating it (p. 28). Akoev et al. (2017) found limitations in the ability to evaluate some stages of research activity (p. 50).

The aim of this study is to investigate the institutional readiness and user requirements for the development of NRIMS in the context of this study, the Institutional readiness towards the development of a research information management system" refers to an organization's current capacity and preparedness to implement and effectively utilize a system designed to manage and track research data, publications, projects, and other related information, encompassing aspects like technical infrastructure, staff expertise, data management practices, organizational culture, and leadership support. In the context of this study institutional readiness refers to management readiness, Process readiness, People readiness and technology readiness.

In a similar vein, the study investigated the user requirements for design and development of NRIMS. In the context of this study, a user requirement typically includes features for streamlined research project management, comprehensive data tracking, efficient collaboration, robust reporting capabilities, and secure access control, allowing researchers to effectively plan, execute, monitor, and disseminate research findings across all stages of the research lifecycle;

Problem Statement

It is the duty of every government in general and universities in particular to provide an accountable system for managing the research funds and publication outputs of the academic staff for national development. However, observations have shown that no single or unified research and information management system in Nigerian universities can tell the story of a university, providing insight into the research landscape: the funding that has been secured; the expertise of researchers; the collaborations that are taking place within and beyond the institution, nationally and globally; the impact of the research

and related publications; and effects on the university's scholarly reputation. Joint (2008) points out that in a climate of evaluation, a university's research needs to be as visible as possible (p. 574).

Despite the significance of RIMS observation by the researchers have shown little or no adoption of research information systems is available in universities in Northwest Nigeria. Nigeria currently lacks similar standards nationally and locally at different universities although this research project is trying to develop a prototype or draft RIMs that could serve as a standard tentatively titled the Nigerian Research Information Management Systems, covering type of activity, fields of research and socio-economic objectives. The existing systems found were developed using the system centre approach that does not take into consideration the institutional readiness and user requirements in the design and development of such systems. Furthermore, most of the available systems in the universities are not designed based on the challenges encountered by the users while using the systems.

It is against this background that this research investigated the institutional readiness and user requirements for the design and development of NRIMS in universities in Northwest Nigeria. Findings from this study will go a long way to providing intensive and quality data that is highly competitive locally as well as globally, that are crucial for strategic decision-making, planning, impact measurement and benchmarking. The development of Nigerian Research Information Management Systems (NRIMS) can provide many advantages. This is because NRIMS can help track the scholarly and community activities of academic staff to aid in career development, tenure and evaluation processes.

Research Objectives:

This study aims to investigate the institutional readiness and user requirements for the design and development of Nigerian research information management systems for universities in Northwest Nigeria. Specifically, this study is designed to:

1. find out the level of institutional readiness towards the development of NRIMS by the universities in the Northwest, Nigeria.
2. determine the user requirements for the design and development for NRIMS for Universities under study

3. identify the challenges associated with the design and development for NRIMS for Universities in Northwest, Nigeria.

Methodology

This research employed a quantitative research approach. The quantitative research approach is the most suitable methodology for this study due to the following reasons: objectivity, generalizability, precision, reliability, time and cost efficiency, scalability, comparison and benchmarking which are the major basis for this research to be undertaken to design and develop the NRIMS. Quantitative research instruments, such as online survey and questionnaire were developed by the researchers to gather data from researchers, and research administrators, in Northwest Nigeria, and it was tested for reliability coefficient of 0.897 ensuring that the data collected was consistent and dependable. An online survey was conducted for the study because of its capability in reducing data collection time and costs. The quantitative data collected was analyzed using SPSS statistical software, descriptive statistics were used and levels of measurement developed by Ruikar et al; (2006) were also used providing a range of analytical techniques to identify patterns, trends, and correlations. The population of the study comprised 165 respondents which were selected using simple random sampling techniques, they included 21 research administrators, 105 researchers, 35 librarians and 7 university management staff.

Results and Discussion

Effective research management is crucial for strengthening Nigeria's research ecosystem. Research Management Systems (RMS) can play a vital role by streamlining processes, improving data collection, and promoting transparency. However, successful implementation hinges on institutional readiness and a deep understanding of user requirements. Developing effective Nigerian Research Information Management Systems (NRIMS) requires careful consideration of both institutional readiness and user requirements. Here's a breakdown of these key aspects:

RQ1: What is the level of institutional readiness towards the development of NRIMS by the universities in the Northwest, Nigeria. In the context of this study institutional readiness refers to management readiness, Process readiness, People readiness and technology readiness as presented by the data collected below: The data was collected and analysed using likert scales of three scales i.e. Disagree (DA), Undecided (U) and Agree (A). While mean (X) and standard deviation (SD) were also used to analysed data for decision making.

Table 1: Management Readiness for the Development of NRIMS

Statement on the Management Readiness	DA	U	A	X	SD
1 Management is keenly interested in working with NRIMS technologies	34 (20.60)	32 (19.39)	99 (60)	3.20	1.13
2 Management recognised the importance and benefits of adopting and using NRIMS tools in our practice of building design and research management	57 (34.54)	13 (7.88)	94 (56.97)	3.12	1.32
3 Management is ready to align the research process to achieve NRIM implementation in practice	42 (25.45)	25 (15.15)	88 (53.33)	3.13	1.36
4 Management is ready to provide policy for training and capacity building to keep academic staff and research administrators up to date with NRIMS tools	51 (30.91)	23 (19.94)	86 (52.12)	2.97	1.52
5 Management is aware of the successes recorded by using NRIMS tools in research management	52 (31.52)	29 (17.58)	84 (50.91)	2.80	1.47
6 Management is aware of NRIMS technology and its benefits to the research practices	69 (41.82)	69 (41.82)	24 (14.55)	2.73	1.03
7 Management has Change management strategies that will ensure successful migration to NRIMS based practices	71 (43.03)	72 (43.64)	15 (9.09)	2.70	1.18
8 Management has developed business strategies that will drive successful NRIMS adoption in organization	72 (43.64)	63 (38.18)	22 (13.33)	2.67	1.09
9 Management has provided adequate financial resources to facilitate NRIMS development in practices	62 (37.58)	72 (43.64)	31 (18.79)	2.40	1.33

Table 1 presented the results of the management readiness of the universities under study. The findings show that out of the eight (9) items measuring management readiness, only 5 statements meet the criteria of agreement by the respondents. From Table 1, statements 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 have a percentage score of 50.91% and above which shows that more than half of the respondents in the universities under study agreed with the statements on those items. This mirrors the fact that more than half of the respondents indicated that they agreed with the management readiness of the universities, while less than half did not agree. In corroboration and considering the levels of measurement

developed by Ruikar et al; (2006) on the analytical framework for the readiness and adoption of computerized research management system, it can be concluded that the mean score of the 5 items is above average decision mean of 2.86 Thus, 3.20, 3.12, 3.13, 2.97 and 2.80 for statement 1,2,3, 4 and 5 respectively in all the elements of process readiness that have the percentage score of 50.91% and above assessed. Therefore, the results show that the universities under study can be said to be partially ready in terms of management readiness.

Table 2: Process Readiness for development of NRIMS

Statement on the Process Readiness	DA	U	A	X	SD
1 Use of NRIMS tools will facilitate and improve faster and more cost-effective research processes	56 (39.94)	20 (12.12)	89 (53.94)	3.93	1.17
2 Use of NRIMS tools will improve integration of research process and research management	48 (29.09)	29 (17.58)	88 (53.33)	3.77	1.22
3 Research process supports and encourages interdisciplinary/inter departmental collaboration	61 (36.97)	19 (11.52)	85 (51.51)	3.47	1.01
4 Existing research processes are flexible enough to accommodate NRIMS technologies	58 (35.15)	23 (13.94)	84 (50.91)	3.37	1.27
5 The design can help identify the bottlenecks and inefficiencies in current research process	57 (34.54)	21 (12.73)	75 (45.45)	3.07	1.14
6 Made changes to current business (where necessary) to facilitate the adoption of NRIMS technologies	62 (37.58)	16 (9.70)	74 (44.85)	2.60	1.16
7 The new design web-based information sharing system can help supports collaboration of the research process from all disciplines	52 (31.52)	18 (10.91)	65 (39.39)	2.53	1.28
8 The development of NRIMS tools helps to exchange information about research internally (within the organization) and externally with other professionals in the research practice	62 (37.58)	13 (7.88)	56 (33.94)	2.47	1.28
Average decision mean= 3.15 (the decision mean is the sum of items mean divided by the number of items)					

Table 2 presented the results of the process readiness of the universities under study. The findings show that out of the eight (8) items measuring the process readiness, only 4 statements meet the criteria of agreement by the respondents. From Table 2, items 1, 2, 3 and 4 have a percentage score of 50.91% and above which shows that more than half of the respondents in the universities under study agreed with the statements on those items. This symbolizes that more than half of the respondents indicated that they agreed with the process readiness of their universities, while less than half did not agree. In corroboration and considering the levels of measurement developed by Ruikar et al;

(2006) on the analytical framework for the readiness and adoption of computerized research management system, it can be concluded that the mean score of the 4 items is above average decision mean of 3.15. Thus, 3.93, 3.77, 3.47 and 3.37 for statement 1,2,3 and respectively in all the elements of process readiness that have the percentage score of 50.91% and above assessed. Therefore, the results show that the universities under study can be said to be partially ready in terms of process readiness.

Table 3: People Readiness on the Development of NRIM

	Statement on the People Readiness	DA	U	A	X	SD
1	People have the ability to implement change and move quickly to adopt and use the NRIM tools	42 (25.45)	22 (13.33)	101 (61.21)	3.80	0.93
2	Staff fully understand the importance of training required for using NRIM tools	38 (23.03)	29 (17.58)	98 (59.39)	3.70	1.09
3	Qualified IT staff that can manage the NRIM operations with other professionals	39 (23.64)	30 (10.30)	96 (50.30)	3.67	1.12
4	Staff have recognized the importance and benefits of adopting and using the NRIM tools in research practice and management	50 (30.30)	28 (16.97)	87 (52.73)	3.60	1.19
5	Staff have the necessary computer literacy, functional expertise and skills to use the NRIM tools	51 (30.91)	28 (16.97)	86 (52.12)	3.53	1.38
6	Research administrators have adequate knowledge on the use of NRIM tools	54 (23.73)	26 (15.76)	85 (51.52)	3.50	1.25
7	The management encourages all staff to learn and use NRIM tools in all research management and practices	52 (31.52)	40 (24.24)	73 (44.24)	3.20	1.27
8	Staff are committed to addressing any issues/inhibitions that may have about using NRIM tools	48 (29.09)	45 (27.27)	72 (43.64)	3.10	1.16
9	Current organizational structure provides an environment that is well suited for NRIM adoption and use	47 (28.48)	47 (28.48)	71 (43.03)	3.03	1.33
10	NRIM managers/users have adequate knowledge of the business processes with NRIM tools	56 (33.94)	17 (10.30)	59 (35.76)	2.97	1.25
11	Training procedures will be provided to enable staff to effectively use NRIM tools	34 (20.61)	16 (9.70)	70 (42.42)	2.93	1.39
12.	The development process will identify and clearly defined roles and responsibilities of staff who use (or will use) NRIM tools	61 (36.70)	15 (9.09)	46 (27.88)	2.90	1.13
Average (decision mean= 3.33						

Table 3 presented the results of the people’s readiness of the universities under study. The findings show that out of the twelve (12) items measuring people’s readiness only 8 statements meet the criteria of agreement by the respondents. From Table 3, statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 have a percentage score of 51.52% and above which shows that majority of the respondents in the universities under study have agreed with the statements on those items. This symbolizes that majority of respondents indicated that they agreed with the people’s readiness of their universities. In corroboration and considering the levels of measurement developed by Ruikar et al; (2006) on the analytical framework for the readiness and adoption of computerized research management system, it can be concluded that the mean score of the 4 items is above average decision mean of 3.33. Thus, 3.80, 3.70, 3.67, 3.60, 3.53 and 3.50 for statement 1,2,3, 4,5,6,7 and 8 respectively in all the elements of people’s readiness that have the percentage score of 51.52% and above assessed. Therefore, the results show that the universities under study can be said to be partially ready in terms of people’s readiness.

Table 4: Technology Readiness on the Development of NRIM

Statement on the Technology Readiness	DA	U	SA	X	SD
1 Adequate infrastructure (computer systems and software) to support NRIM adoption in our university	45 (27.27)	22 (13.33)	98 (59.39)	3.50	1.38
2 Effective intranet and extranet facilities to facilitate information sharing and interoperability in working with NRIM tools	46 (27.88)	23 (13.94)	96 (58.18)	3.43	1.47
3 Familiar with the use of specialist software applications related to expertise	54 (32.73)	25 (15.15)	86 (52.12)	3.35	1.32
Average (decision mean= 3.43					

Table 4 presented the results of the Technology readiness of the universities under study. The findings show that all the three (3) items measuring technological readiness such as (adequate infrastructure, specialist software application and effective intranet and extranet facilities) only 2 statements meet the criteria of agreement by the respondents. From Table 4, statements 1 and 2, have a percentage score of 59.39 and 58.18% which shows that majority of the respondents in the universities under study have agreed with the statements on those items. This mirrors the fact that majority of respondents indicated that they agreed with the technology readiness of their universities. Though, the last statement on table 4, despite scoring 52.12% with a mean of 3.35, did not meet the criterion mean of 3.43. In corroboration and considering the levels of measurement developed by Ruikar et al; (2006) on the analytical framework for the readiness and

adoption of computerized research management system, it can be concluded that the mean score of the 2 items is above average decision mean of 3.43. Thus, 3.50 and 3.43, for statement 1 and 2 respectively in the two elements of technology readiness that have a percentage score of 58.18% and above assessed. Therefore, the results show that the universities under study can be said to be ready in terms of technology readiness.

RQ 2. What are the user requirements for the design and development for NRIMS for Universities in Northwest, Nigeria. Table 5 presented the user requirements of the respondents with regards to the design and development of NRIMS in Universities in Northwest Nigeria.

Table 5: Users Requirement for Development of NRIMS

Statement on the User Requirements	DA	U	A	X	SD
1 User Registration: The system should allow users to create an account by providing necessary information such as username, email address, and password. It should also include a verification process to ensure the security of user accounts.	47 (28.48)	13 (7.88)	105 (63.64)	3.80	0.93
2 Product Search and Filtering: The system should enable users to search for products based on various criteria such as keywords, categories, or price ranges. It should also provide filtering options to narrow search results based on specific attributes or preferences.	44 (26.67)	18 (10.91)	103 (62.42)	3.70	1.09
3 Online Ordering and Payment: The system should allow users to add products to a shopping cart, proceed with the checkout process, and make secure online payments using different payment methods such as credit cards or digital wallets.	47 (28.48)	17 (10.30)	101 (62.21)	3.67	1.12
4 Consistent Visual Design: The system should adhere to a consistent visual design throughout the user interface, including color schemes, typography, and graphical elements. This consistency helps create a cohesive and recognizable brand identity.	42 (25.45)	25 (15.15)	98 (59.39)	3.60	1.19
5 Clear Call-to-Action Buttons: The system should use clear and visually distinct call-to-action buttons to guide users toward desired actions, such as "Add to Cart," "Submit," or "Confirm." These buttons should be placed strategically and have sufficient visual prominence.	54 (32.72)	14 (8.48)	97 (58.79)	3.53	1.38

6 Intuitive Form Design: The system should design forms with clear labels, input validation, and appropriate field types. It should provide helpful hints or tooltips where necessary to assist users in completing forms accurately and efficiently	35 (21.21)	36 (21.82)	94 (56.97)	3.50	1.25
7 Responsive Design: The system should be responsive and adapt seamlessly to different screen sizes and devices, providing optimal user experience on desktops, laptops, tablets, and smartphones.	47 (28.48)	37 (22.42)	81 (49.09)	3.20	1.27
8 Intuitive Navigation: The system should have a clear and intuitive navigation structure, enabling users to find their desired information or functionalities easily. It should include logical menus, breadcrumbs, and search capabilities to enhance user navigation.	49 (29.70)	37 (22.42)	79 (47.88)	3.10	1.16
9 Error Handling: The system should display informative and user-friendly error messages whenever users encounter errors or input invalid data. It should provide clear instructions on how to rectify errors and prevent data loss.	43 (26.06)	17 (10.30)	71 (43.03)	3.03	1.33
Average (decision mean= 3.46)					

Table 5 presented the results of users' requirements for the design and development of NRIMS in the universities of Northwest under study. The findings show that out of the nine (9) items measuring users' requirements only 6 statements meet the criteria of agreement by the respondents. From Table 5, statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 have a percentage score of 56.97% and above which shows that majority of the respondents in the universities under study agreed with the statements on those items. This implies that majority of respondents indicated that they agreed with the users' requirements for design and development.

In corroboration and considering the levels of measurement developed by Ruikar et al; (2006) on the analytical framework for the readiness and adoption of computerized research management system, it can be concluded that the mean score of the 6 items is above average decision mean of 3.46. Thus, 3.80, 3.70, 3.67, 3.60, 3.53, and 3.50, for statement 1,2,3,4,5, and 6 respectively in the elements of users' requirements that have the percentage score of 56.97% and above assessed. Therefore, the results show that the universities under study can be said to require the following elements (User Registration, Product Search and Filtering, Online Ordering and Payment, Consistent

Visual Design, Clear Call-to-Action Buttons, Intuitive Form Design) for the design and development of NRIMS.

RQ 3. What are the challenges associated with the design and development for NRIMS for Universities in Northwest, Nigeria. For this research the challenges are presented as follows:

Table 6: Challenges Associated with the design and development for NRIMS for Universities in Northwest, Nigeria

SN	Challenges	Freq.	%
1	Inadequate funding by the universities	150	90.91
2	Lack of infrastructure	145	87.88
3	Limited technical expertise	137	83.03
4	Poor data management practice	134	81.21
5	Long term reliance on legacy system	67	40.61
6	Lack of technological equipment	65	39.39
7	Inadequate Data Subscription	56	33.94
8	Poor financial investment in infrastructure for data management	50	30.30
9	Lack of analysis and data mining	45	27.27
10	Inconsistent pattern of information system	43	26.06
11	Low data bandwidth	42	25.45
12	Unauthorized access to sensitive information	40	24.24
13	Lack of skilled professionals	41	24.85
14	Absence of IT policy	38	23.03
15	Absence of collaborations between the units in the universities	39	23.64

Table 6 presents the challenges associated with the design and development of NRIMS in the universities in the northwest Nigeria. The study reveals that the most predominant challenges associated with the design and development of NRIMS in Northwest Nigerian universities include Inadequate funding 150 (90.91%), lack of infrastructure 145 (87.88%), Limited technical expertise 137 (83.03%), Poor data management practices 134 (81.21%). This is followed by long term reliance on legacy system 67 (40.61%), Lack of technological equipment 65(39.39%), Inadequate Data Subscription 56 (33.94%). While challenges by universities under study in terms of design and development of NRIMS were absence of collaborations between the units in the universities 39(23.64%) and absence of IT policy 38(23.03%). This mirrors that the challenges associated with the

design and development of NRIMS in Northwest Nigerian universities are complex and multifaceted.

Discussion of the findings

From the above findings it is obvious to note that all the universities in the Northwest have shown that they are partially ready for the design and development of NRIMS due to the percentage scores in the frequency and the mean of the elements in the gullwing parameters of management, process, people and technology readiness. This finding corroborates with the study of Göpfert et al., (2014) who found that web-based platforms required to have high score in the institutional readiness index of an institutions before the deployment is done, which enable them to manage and disseminate their research outputs including improved research visibility, enhanced collaboration, and increased research impact (Angelo et al., 2015).

The findings also show that the universities under study can be said to require the following elements (User Registration, Product Search and Filtering, Online Ordering and Payment, Consistent Visual Design, Clear Call-to-Action Buttons, Intuitive Form Design) for the design and development of NRIMS. The findings also found that the challenges associated with the design and development of NRIMS in Northwest Nigerian universities are complex and multifaceted, these challenges were significant funding constraints, lack the necessary infrastructure, technical expertise, poor data management practices which hinder their ability to invest in NRIMS. This finding contradicts the study of Korberg (2016), who found that a lack of faculty engagement due to time constraints and administrative burden was one of the anticipated barriers to the proposed RIMS (p. 26).

In similar vein, the findings are in contrast with the challenges reported by institutions included increased workload (Bevan & Harrington, 2011; Buchmayer et al., 2014), the need to develop new skills, the engagement of stakeholders (Bevan & Harrington, 2011, p. 29), difficulties in ingesting information into the system (Grenz et al., 2017, p. 178), and creating a comprehensive research information management environment (Grenz et al., 2017, p. 180). Jeffery and Asserson (2008) articulate the advantages of formal metadata and identify issues regarding interoperability of metadata in CRIS (p. 79). Bevan and Harrington (2011) note the trade-off between data quality in the CRIS and workload for those entering and validating it (p. 28). Akoev et al. (2017) found limitations in the ability to evaluate some stages of research activity (p. 50).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the identification of institutional readiness and user requirements for design and development of NRIMS can effectively improve the efficiency of research management in the Universities of the Northwest Nigeria, with minimal challenges. This article analyzed the current institutional readiness and user requirements status of the universities in terms of design and development of research information systems. In response to its status, some challenges have been identified that have affected how systems can be designed and developed. This article also provides valuable insights for developing effective NRIMS in Nigeria. It is hoped that the findings of the study will help the universities in Northwest Nigeria, the research management centers and offices, adopting and implementing NRIMS to facilitate a robust and granular analysis of research activity and the identification of research trends of their universities.

In future research endeavors, Continuous Assessment (CA) must consistently evolve to align with the evolving user requirements of the NRIMS in university administration, thereby enhancing its efficacy. This adaptive approach will offer more effective support in advancing the development of diverse research activities within universities providing researchers with a convenient location to submit, modify, or renew their Research Compliance related information such as protocol approval requests. The design and development of NRIMS will also provide a centralized and integrated database for the administrative units to manage related issues such as ensuring prior approval before the use of hazardous materials, suitability of location of use, adequate training and medical surveillance of staff, appropriateness of protective equipment measures, etc.

Recommendations:

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Universities should prioritize more investment in ICT infrastructure, and provision of technical expertise boost the readiness of the universities to support the design and development of NRIMS and their research endeavors.
2. Universities should provide more funding to support the users' requirements for the design and development of NRIMS
3. Universities should develop strategic partnerships with technological companies to access expertise, resources, and funding that will help them to overcome the

challenges associated with the readiness and requirement for the design and development of NRIMS

4. Universities in Northwest Nigeria should build the capacity of their staff to design, develop and maintain NRIMS.

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